

INSTRUCTIONS FOR CREATING WEBSITES

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ANNOTATION

This article is recommended for students and young programmers as a guide for the simplest, most comfortable and easy to create websites.

Keywords and phrases: Web-site, Tags, HTML hypertext markup language, Visual HTML-editor - Adobe Dream Weaver, Web designer, domain and hosting, server, database server, ftp-server.

POSTING THE SITE ON THE INTERNET

Create a website (a site or website is one or more logically linked web pages; as well as the location of server content. We offer you the simplest and most understandable methods. First, the site is HTML (English HyperText Markup Language - a standardized document markup language for viewing web pages in the browser). Web browsers HTTP (English HyperText Transfer Protocol is a practical-level data transfer protocol, originally in the form of hypertext documents in HTML format, now it is used to transfer data arbitrarily).

It retrieves an HTML document from a server via HTTPS protocols or opens it from a local disk, then interprets the code into an interface that is displayed on a monitor screen. can be created using the hypertext markup language.

In the text editor, they are marked with special tabs called text tags that they want to place on the pages of the site.

```
<HTML>
```

```
<HEAD>
```

```
TITLE
```

```
</HEAD>
```

```
<BODY>
```

```
<H1 STYLE = "COLOR : RED;"> HELLO DUSTIM </H1>
```

```
<IMG SRC = 'RASM_NOMI.JPG'>
```

```
</BODY>
```

```
</HTML>
```

WHAT ARE NICE TAGS?

Tags - indicates what the text should look like. The first is to separate the tags from the text and are located inside the square brackets.

Second, a document prepared in a word processor is stored as a web page in HTML format.

Third, you can use custom software - visual HTML editors or website creators.

Visual HTML Editor - Adobe Dream Weaver (Dreamweaver is a visual HTML editor from Adobe. Originally developed and supported by Macromedia up to version 8. Later versions of Dreamweaver CS3 were released by Adobe).

Web designers are professionals who design a website structure, as well as choose ways to present information and design a web project.

A web designer needs to know modern web technologies and have an artistic background, no matter what tools you use to create a site, you must first think about its content and structure. Suppose you go to a biology circle and decide to create a website for that circle. The content of the site should reflect the creative life of the members of the circle in order to attract similar ideas. It is necessary to determine the structure of the site - the general content is divided into separate pages, indicating the semantic sections and the links between them. The site may contain general information.

The program and schedule of lessons, the place of training.

1. News and announcements page.
2. Complex of medicinal plants.
3. The full name of the leader.
4. Personal pages of the head and members of the circle.
5. Necessary and Useful references.

To other sources on the Internet and so on. Basically, the site is downloaded from the main home page, which must first answer the question of what this site is about: To do this, the title of the image is placed on the main page, a short text that records the content of the site. Also, the main menu and link of the section can place the name of the author of the site and his contact information, as well as the counter of visitors to the news.

On each page of the site, as a rule, there are several permanent elements located in the same places.

SITE NAME

It should be located at the top of the page.

MAIN MENU

It is usually located on the left side of the page, and the number of menu items, their names and order do not change on all pages of the site.

It is good that the pages of the site are prepared in the same style. To maintain the style, and often develop a site page template that presents the elements that are present on all pages of the site at the beginning.

The procedure for filling the pages of the site with information materials is to follow the following recommendations:

1. If it is a single sentence, do not put a full stop in the names of sites and pages.
2. Write the names of the menu items briefly.
3. The name of the object cannot be written in several lines.
4. Do not choose not to set a background for the pages, it will be difficult to read the text on such a background.
5. Don't put too much information and art blocks on the page.

6. Don't write too long texts: Divide the text into small paragraphs, separating them with blank lines.

7. Use the same formatting methods for each paragraph.

Site hosting on the Internet is the artificial final stage of site creation.

Before posting a site, all of this internet should encourage you to try the text to make sure it is displayed correctly in different browsers. The texts read well against the selected background.

Pictures in the face, the bridges provide the right transition.

We will tell you about the tasks of creating a website, hosting and domains, as well as the tasks of their operation in the Internet world, as well as the difference between them.

So:

Why hosting and domain? Domain and hosting are basic services, without which it is impossible to create any website on the Internet. Hosting is a service to host a site on a server that is constantly on the Internet: Hosting can be paid or free.

Paid hosting is commonly used by large companies to host Google sites. At the same time, they make it easier to read and remember this secondary name, which may match the company name. Individuals can use free hosting for their sites, their options are limited compared to paid options. What is the difference between a domain and a host? The domain is the online address of the site and the hosting for the site is the "living" place. To create a website, you must first register a domain and then order a hosting service.

Why do you need a website hosting? Pay attention,

any site is actually a collection of files (texts, images, videos, program scripts, databases, etc.).

But why do you need website hosting? So that internet users can see it in general. It is not enough to have site files on your computer, you just need to upload them to the network.

Site files are downloaded to computers with special software. They are called servers. The servers are online 24 hours a day, ensuring the uninterrupted operation of the site and protecting it from malicious attacks. To host site files, you need to rent space on the server or the entire server if the site has a lot of content and is aimed at a wide flow of visitors. So, hosting is, in simple terms, opportunity and space rental.

You can, of course, try to host your site on your PC: re-read many forums, try to configure the software (web server, database server, ftp server, etc.), set a static IP address for the site, Internet channel and electrical supply. But, unfortunately, it is almost impossible to guarantee the availability and uninterrupted operation of all the elements in the house: for example, you may face power outages or problems with the Internet. In addition, a ton of information is required about network setup and how network protocols work.

Virtual hosting allows you to avoid all the hassles at once. Paid web hosting already includes all the necessary components to make your website work reliably.

HOSTING

- customized software;
- uninterruptible power supply;
- reliable Internet channel;
- 7/24 professional help.

There are different types of web hosting: shared hosting, VPS, dedicated and more. To find out how one type of hosting differs from another and which tariff is better to choose, we would recommend reading information on this topic in various publications and on the Internet.

Limitations: small disk space, limit on single file size, given name, only third level and so on, but they are enough for users' home pages and non-profit sites.

The main drawback: when placing your site, the company independently adds commercial advertising on its Facebook page.

You can find a list of servers that provide hosting by searching for a free hosting query.

Outcome: students and young programmers

USED PUBLICATIONS

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